

A close-up photograph of several stacked logs, showing the circular cross-sections of the wood. The wood grain is clearly visible, with concentric growth rings. The logs are piled together, with some showing dark, textured bark. A semi-transparent dark horizontal band is overlaid across the middle of the image, containing white text.

THINK NATURE CONCEPT DOCUMENT #5

Biodiversity credits and offsets

Biodiversity credits and offsets

By Think Nature's science team

Executive summary. Ecological damage caused by infrastructure projects or other activity can be compensated by the application of nature-friendly actions in a process called *biodiversity offsetting*. The typical goal of offsetting is *no-net-loss*, which means that ecological *net losses* must be fully compensated by commensurate *net gains*. Estimation of net loss should account for the size of area impacted, its ecological condition and the degree of impact expected. Losses from both outright habitat conversion and increased disturbance should be accounted for. To implement the offsets, one can use common types of nature-friendly actions: protection, habitat restoration, and habitat maintenance. *Net positive impact* can be achieved if offsets are larger than what would be needed for no-net-loss.

There are fifteen or so design factors that influence the credibility, feasibility, and costs of offsetting. These factors can be grouped under *aims*, decisions about the *spatial aspects* and *timing* of offsets, *measurement* of biodiversity, and the properties of *offsets actions*. One critical design component is the response of biodiversity to the offset actions taken, which can be summarized and quantified by a time-response function. The response function is introduced here, because it is also relevant for the evaluation of *biodiversity credits*.

As part of the *mitigation hierarchy*, offsets are closely related to impact avoidance and minimization, which can be implemented via nature-friendly spatial design and technical impact avoidance measures. Impact avoidance, offsets, habitat banking, biodiversity credits and payments for ecosystem services are all themes that can cross paths with business interests. In some cases, operational permits may require the implementation of offsets. Overall, the theme of impact avoidance is very important for the interaction between nature and people.

While there is broad global interest in both biodiversity offsets and credits, there are also concerns about risks. The causes of offset failure include systemic failure of offset policy, incompetent project-level design, poor enforcement of implementation, and failure of monitoring, verification, and accounting. Such concerns should be addressed with competent and transparent design and implementation.

This document is #5 in Think Nature's series of concept notes provided as a public service for those interested in understanding the interaction of people and biodiversity. Overall offsetting and biodiversity credits are a broad topic and the present text is only a brief introduction.

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1. Offsets in the framework of the mitigation hierarchy

While offsets can also be done on their own, they are usually positioned as the fourth step of the so-called *mitigation hierarchy*, in which negative ecological impacts are

- i) avoided
- ii) minimized locally
- iii) reduced by habitat restoration in the impacted area
- iv) offset by restoration, protection, or other nature-friendly actions elsewhere.

The avoidance and minimization steps are applied first to ensure that the project footprint is small and located in habitats that have as little importance for biodiversity or ecosystem services as possible. From the perspective of nature, a good construction project location would be an area that has already been heavily degraded. The mitigation hierarchy is best considered during the early stages of project planning, when alternative plans are developed.

The main components of impact minimization are spatial impact avoidance (TN Concept Note #4) and reduction of disturbance and indirect impacts by technical solutions. Complete impact avoidance may not always be possible: for example, resource extraction is only possible where the resource is located.

Biodiversity offsets can be applied to residual ecological damage that could not be avoided. They mean ecological compensation of the ecological losses caused by construction, development, land use or other human activities. Offsets resemble the *polluter pays* -principle, but with offsets the compensation is done for nature, not people. Overall, offsets are easiest to specify for the project footprint and indirect local impacts. At present, there are no generally accepted methodologies for the offsetting of scope 3 impacts that become distributed via business procurement and value chains (TN Concept Note #2). This is because scope 3 impacts become distributed in small bits across the world, which makes offset design, implementation, and verification very difficult.

Offsets would be implemented using the same kinds of nature-friendly actions that can be used for biodiversity conservation: protection, habitat restoration and habitat maintenance (TN Concept Note #3). The main constraint is the following: with offsets, it must be possible to quantify the gains produced by the action. This has implications to the level of knowledge required of the action. Effectively, there must be some quantitative estimate of the response of biodiversity to the action (section 3).

Figure 1. The fundamental principle of NNL offsets. Accounting for size of offset area, effectiveness of nature-friendly actions and safety margins for uncertainties (etc.), net gains must be larger than net losses.

The goal of offsetting is usually *no net loss* (NNL), which means that all net losses to biodiversity are fully compensated by commensurate net gains achieved via said offset actions (Fig. 1). If more is done than needed for NNL, then the aim is Net Positive Impact (NPI; section 4). Complications arise in the operational definition of NNL (next section).

The main principle of offsets is easy to understand, but the details of offset design are not simple. The methods and calculations needed in the context of *biodiversity credits* would be very similar to those needed for the quantification of offset gains.

2. The basics of offset design

Effectively, one needs to answer the questions: what is lost, where and when? What is gained, where, and when? In this evaluation, net gains must come out as larger than net losses. The operational question becomes: how are losses and gains calculated and for what components of biodiversity?

Evaluation of losses is relatively easy – although by no means trivial. One possible approach is to base it on the habitat-level concept of *habitat hectares*. A habitat hectare [hha] is a standardized unit of loss,

corresponding to 1 ha of habitat in effectively natural condition. Ecological condition [hha/ha] becomes reduced with human impacts; condition zero corresponds to something that is completely unfunctional as a habitat and condition one to natural state. When using hha, loss L can be estimated as: $L=I\times A\times C$, in which I is the strength of impact (fraction lost), A is the physical size of the impacted area, and C is the condition of the area prior to new impact. Loss becomes larger when the impacted area grows, when it is in relatively high condition, and when the impact is strong (= large fraction lost).

Figure 2 summarizes the five main design axes of offsets, which are relevant for the estimation of gains. There are fifteen (or so) factors that effectively determine the credibility, feasibility, and costs of an offsetting effort. Answering these questions and information needs allows the calculation of the size of the area in which offsets need to be implemented for NNL to be achieved in a credible manner.

Figure 2. Five main axes of offset design. Additionally, there are separate issues of administration, verification, and monitoring. See text for details.

Briefly characterized, the main lines of design are as follows. With respect to *objectives*, it is very important how strictly the mitigation hierarchy is utilized. When there is more avoidance and minimization, there is less need for offsets. NNL will need a definition and there will need to be a decision whether NPI is set as the goal. With respect to *space*, there needs to be specification of how far offsets can be implemented from the location of losses. A decision is also needed for regulatory frame, which can be some combination of local, national, and international.

There are two major questions that concern *time*. The first is the evaluation time frame, which is explained in the context of biodiversity response functions (section 3). Also, it is a critical decision that offsets are made permanent, as use of temporary offsets allows failure of NNL via the combination of temporary gains with semi-permanent losses.

With respect to *biodiversity*, there are major decisions around biodiversity measurement. Effectively, decisions need to be made about the level of habitat type classification used and possible species-level measurement. The concept of ‘*trading up*’ refers to the possibility that certain habitats or species can be replaced with other habitats or species, which are seen as ecologically more valuable.

There are several important design factors around *actions*. The per-area-unit gains from restoration, management and protection need to be estimated (next section). *Additionality* and *leakage* are two major concepts. It must be verified that the offset actions proposed are additional; that they would not have been

implemented otherwise. This requirement of additionality effectively means that double-counting of gains is not allowed. Leakage means relocation of human pressures from a newly protected location to another location, which reduces the net-effectiveness of action.

It is obvious from this top-level description that offset design is not a trivial task. One major component is estimation of the gains characteristic to any given nature-friendly action (next section). The same way of estimating gains can be used in the context of *biodiversity credits*, which can be seen as gains that have been produced in advance and stored into a *habitat bank* for potential later use in some project.

3. Generating gains and credits; the biodiversity response

Axiom: Gains from a nature-friendly action only depend on the mechanistic effects of the action, not on the motivation of those doing the action.

The same action (TN Concept Document #3) can be used in multiple contexts: as a voluntary courtesy to nature, as part of compulsory biodiversity offsets, or to develop biodiversity credits. The generic question is, how to quantify the effectiveness of an action? A simplified generic answer is, develop a biodiversity response function based on scientific literature and possibly expert judgment.

The *response function* describes how *habitat condition* (~vegetation condition, vegetation integrity, naturalness) or some structurally analogous measure of biodiversity changes through time after the implementation of nature-friendly action. Examination of a response function reveals why an evaluation time frame must be set for the calculation of offset gains and credits (Fig. 3). Setting of the evaluation time frame is a partially subjective decision, which can be illustrated with an example.

Assume that a lawn is planted into a forest-to-be, and an expert is asked, what improvement in the ecological condition of forest is to be expected? Assume that the answer is condition 0.7, meaning it will eventually become good forest. However, this number is useless on its own. For it to have meaning, it must be tied to a time frame in the form “an improvement of 0.xx is expected in y years.” In the case of a forest, its maturation would take many decades if not centuries. It is not acceptable that instant gains of 0.7 are assumed, if such a high ecological condition can only be reached in, e.g., a century (Fig. 3, point C).

Figure 3. Illustrating important properties of a response function. Note that (A) mean gain over years 0 – 25, (B) mean gain over years 25 - 50, and (C) the point estimate of gain at year 100 are completely different. Please see text for importance.

Gains should be calculated from a time frame that is societally acceptable in the context of compensation for effectively immediate losses. Figure 3 uses a 25-year time frame for illustration. Looking at the gain function for our hypothetical forest, it is obvious that mean gains over the first 25 years are less than 0.1, a number very different from the point estimate of 0.7 at year 100 (point C). The length of the evaluation time frame will influence the numbers that come out, which is why an evaluation time frame has to be specified. If one is not specified explicitly, one will be assumed implicitly.

This brings us to the evaluation time frame and two reasons why generating biodiversity credits in advance is good. First, there is less uncertainty about biodiversity credits have been generated in advance compared to offsets that are implemented in the future. Second, if the action has been done in advance, then gains will be higher, because the mean is calculated from a ‘higher’ section of the response function (Fig. 3, sections A vs B). Gains from both protection and restoration start from zero at the time the action is done and increase through time (Fig. 3). In case of restoration, the habitat improves and species return with variable time delays (TN Concept Note #6A). In the case of protected area establishment, the mechanism of action is reduction of human pressures in the area, which allows gains to accumulate at a rate that corresponds to the landscape-level loss rate of that habitat type, further corrected for leakage.

In summary, a response function should be defined first. Gains can then be evaluated in terms of improvements in the future using a time scale that is meaningful societally and in a business context. Gains in the distant future cannot be taken as credible gains for present-day development projects, which cause immediate losses. Pairing far distant gains with immediate losses is a major technical mechanism for failing NNL.

4. Net Positive Impact / net gain

Net positive impact (NPI) means that ecological losses are compensated beyond NNL, thus delivering ecological net gains – which can be a business sustainability goal. At simplest, NPI can be achieved by increasing the size of offset area from that required by NNL. Table 1 summarizes four mechanisms that can under certain circumstances produce NPI.

Table 1. Four ways of generating NPI. Overall, the *permanence* of offsets is critical for any claims of NPI.

NPI method	Mechanism and timing of gains
Increase of implementation area from NNL	Increase the size of the offset by application of an NPI multiplier. NPI provided by this method is delivered already during the evaluation time frame.
Increase in gains from further improvements in biodiversity response after the end of the evaluation time frame	Offset areas treated with slowly maturing nature-friendly actions will continue to improve for decades, which means that gains continue to increase after the end of the evaluation time frame. This will produce long-term NPI, because the long-term mean gains will be higher than evaluation time frame mean gains, <i>conditional on offsets being permanent.</i>
Combination of temporary losses with permanent gains	Here the point is that e.g. a resource extraction project may be temporary, which means that indirect impacts from noise, traffic (etc.) will end after the project terminates. Consequently, NPI may be generated if the temporary losses have been compensated with

	permanent offsets. This NPI method does not apply, if the losses are permanent, as would be the case e.g. if a new major road is built.
Decrease of direct impacts after the end of the project	This mechanism relates to the third level of the mitigation hierarchy, local restoration in the project area. In this mechanism, the impacted area is restored locally during or after the project, but this restoration is not counted towards reducing the size of the offsets needed. Consequently, all local ecological damage will be compensated using offsetting actions during the evaluation time frame, and any later gains produced by local restoration are left to generate additional NPI.

5. A note on difficulties and concerns

Many scientific papers express concerns about the reliability of biodiversity offsets. Similar concerns transfer to biodiversity credits as well, because the underlying methods for generating ecological gains will be the same. Reasons for offset failure can be broadly divided into systemic failure of offset policy and requirements, failures in project-level design, inadequate implementation, and failures in monitoring, verification, enforcement, and accounting.

Competent design is critical, because a poor offset system will lead to failure of NNL even when projects are officially labelled as successes due to high compliance with (inadequate) legislative requirements. Such failure would happen when policy requirements fail to support credible mathematical-ecological design criteria, including those described above. Lack of regulatory oversight, enforcement, and accounting may allow deficient on-the-ground implementation, and cases are known when offsets were never even implemented at all.

A further complication is the relatively poor measurability of nature and biodiversity, especially at the level of species (see Think Nature Concept Note #6A). For example, population sizes of species vary due to randomness in births and deaths, movement of animals around the landscape, weather, interactions with other species, and background trends such as climate change. Observing and counting individuals in the field includes a random-component of observation. If very accurate ground verification of losses and gains is required, major operational problems will be encountered. Accounting of animals is fundamentally different from the accounting of money.

6. Think Nature's way

Impact avoidance, biodiversity offsets, biodiversity credits, habitat banking and payments for ecosystem services (TN Concept Note #7) are all related themes that may have relevance for the society, businesses, individual land owners and locals impacted by changes in nature. All these aim at reducing and / or compensating past, present, or forthcoming impacts on species and habitats.

Biodiversity offsets, credits and finance are complicated topics due to (i) relatively complicated specification and implementation, (ii) procedural questions of legislation, regulation, and administration, and (iii) natural variability in the state of nature (TN Concept Note #6A), which impacts monitoring and verification. In any larger case there will be many details that go far beyond the basic thoughts described here. Broad understanding will be required about the effectiveness of nature-friendly actions, the design and evaluation of biodiversity offsets/credits, and procedural issues.

Contact us for guidance.

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